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ATM defects result in Xist modulation.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We provide here transcriptome data associated with genetic modulation of the BRCA1-associated DNA damage pathway that demonstrates a role for ATM in Xist activation and repression found in cancer and in cells and tissues resulting from tumor suppressor mutation. The data support a general role for Xist control by HR and non-homologous end joining repair pathways mediated by H2AX, 53bp1, BRCA1, Rif1, and NBS complex component Mre11.